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Evaluating the use of Mock Examinations as a Predictor of Primary School Students' Performance in High Stakes Examinations

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Abstract:

Learning analytics is emerging as a crucial discourse which can be useful in predicting students' academic performance and in qualitative development of learning to redress educational challenges. However, primary school teachers in Botswana seem impervious to the significance of the vast amount of data generated on daily transactions between themselves and students, and/or between students and content. While keeping in mind the enormous quantity of educational data that could result from interactive relationships in the classroom, I sought to assess the predictability of Primary School Leaving Examinations (PSLE) results using mock examinations. A mixed method research employing correlational design underpinned the approach of the study. Secondary data were collected (N = 152) and analyzed using Binary Logistic Regression. Results showed that mock examination scores are a significant predictor of academic success. A logit regression algorithm was derived. Findings provided an alternative strategy to foretell the academic achievement of students. Implications on assessment practices and on teaching and learning are discussed.

Keywords: Assessment, Botswana, Logistic regression, Mock examination, Prediction, Primary school leaving examinations

INTRODUCTION

Current policies and reforms in the education system of Botswana recommend the use of models that promote the quality of education in primary schools. One such document is the Revised National Policy on Education of 1994 (RNEP, 1994), which identifies primary school education as a crucial period because it provides a foundation upon which subsequent levels of education rest. In this light, quality issues in primary education are a concern and problematic in the sense that low quality education may have adverse effects on upper levels of education and the general socio-economic standing of a child later on in life (Bagwasi, 2018; Mphale & Mhlauli, 2014; RNEP, 1994).

One of the primary indicators of the quality of primary education is students' academic achievement. Key stakeholders evaluate academic success in primary schools based on summative assessment outcomes like Primary School Leaving Examination (PSLE) and formative assessment tools like tests, school-based examinations, quizzes and exercises. Assessment of students basically provides primary school educators and the community with diagnostic information upon which they can monitor and evaluate the quality of education in a school (Nenty, Adedoyin, Odili *et al.*, 2007). According to Khine (2018), assessment of students generates

a vast amount of data which can be analyzed to give comprehensive and contextualized information about students and their learning. The general trend of research in education is to find pragmatic reforms towards quality teaching and learning, as well as to improve students' performance. Teacher practices evolve based on their reflections on past experiences, the needs of students, contemporary instructional strategies and approaches. As of recent, there is a trend of research showing interest in an approach called learning analytics, which uses student data to inform decisions about instructional practices. Learning analytics is a discourse which deals with measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of information to provide teachers with the means to take reflexive and targeted action towards enhancing learning experiences and opportunities (Gulbahar & Ilgaz, 2014). The emergence of learning analytics offers crucial opportunities for utilizing feedback effectively as well as for qualitative development of transactions between students and teachers and/or content (Gulbahar & Ilgaz, 2014; Khine, 2018). Nonetheless, learning analytics remains underutilized in primary schools of Botswana.

Rationale of the study

Currently, world-wide assessment practices involve the prediction of whether students will pass or fail (Garton, Dyer & King, 2000; Kuhn, 2015; Trindade & Ferreira, 2021; Yang, Lu, Huang *et al.*, 2018; Yasein, Helali & Mohomad, 2017). The prospect of predicting performance is considered as a daunting endeavor because of the vastness of factors that influence students' academic success. Evidence has shown that factors like location of school (Bulala *et al.*, 2014), gender of students (Ramatlala & Nenty, 2012), teacher judgement (Kuhn, 2015), number of assignments (Yasein *et al.*, 2021) do not significantly predict future performance of students. On the other hand, student attendance, teacher characteristics, and forecast grades have been reported as good predictors of learning success (Thobega & Masole, 2008; Trindade and Ferreira, 2021; Yasein *et al.*, 2021). These findings are inconsistent and seem to vary in relation to context.

In Botswana, the practice of predicting future scores of learners is evident only in secondary schools. Botswana Examination Council and senior secondary schools use forecast scores to predict final grades of students in their terminal examinations (Bulala, Ramatlala & Nenty, 2014; Masole & Utlwang, 2005; Thobega & Masole, 2008). Teachers in Botswana senior secondary school use forecast grades as baselines which are used as reference points for their instructional practices and assessment targets. Therefore, one may ask why are primary schools are not adopting the same practice with regard to predicting PSLE outcomes? As Kumar *et al.* (2017) has pointed out, there appears to be a shortage of investigation on factors that could be used to foretell the academic performance achievement of primary school students in Botswana. Not only that, there is no clear suggestion as to how secondary school teachers compute forecast grades for their students.

Further evidence of poor application of data mining and learning analytics is from a 2014 study carried out by the Ministry of Education and Skills Development (MOESD, 2014: 30) in which they reported that "*monthly tests are not credible, they are not analyzed nor used to provide an overview of performance status*". This concern was raised in response to one of the study's objectives (*Terms of Reference 7*) which looked to determine the quality of assessment and its impact in schools of Kgatleng Region, Teachers in primary schools of Kgatleng region are generating enormous data which remains unutilized.

Purpose of the Study

Therefore, the primary aim of this study was to devise an objective strategy for teachers to use continuous assessment in forecasting academic success of students. Mock examinations were used due to their standardized nature and more especially because they are administered prior to sitting for PSLE, as a dipstick to assess the preparedness of Std 7 students for Primary School Leaving Examination (PSLE). Essentially, this study assessed the contribution of mock examination scores towards performance in PSLE using Binary Logistic Regression analysis, derived a logit regression model from data, and piloted the model to forecast PSLE performance of a cohort of 2023 Std 7 candidates. Two main research questions were answered;

- 1) Does mock examination scores significantly predict PSLE performance of Std 7 students?

2) What is the predicted PSLE performance of 2023 cohort of Std 7 students?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The methodological framework guiding this study was a mixed method approach in which both qualitative and quantitative techniques were employed simultaneously (Creswell, 2015). The dependent variable was categorical whereas the independent variable was continuous. A correlational design with the employment of non-parametric test was used to assess the relationship of mock examination scores towards PSLE performance.

Setting of Study

In Botswana, primary schools fall under the Department of Basic Education. The Ministry of Education and Skills Development has demarcated schools across the country into 10 regional zones. In this study, I took deliberate interest in Kgatleng region, which is located in the south-eastern part of the country. Kgatleng region has jurisdiction over 37 primary schools spread across a diversity of settlements (semi-urban to rural). It is common practice in Kgatleng region that after every assessment of students through monthly tests and termly examinations, primary schools analyses academic results and send reports to the regional office. In turn, a team from the regional office visits individual primary schools to monitor and evaluate school performances with particular interest in standard 7 results (Std 7). This exercise over emphasizes the value of academic success. Primary schools are also concerned with preserving a good image of the school's overall performance in academics.

Sample

Two samples were used in the study; one sample for assessing the contribution of mock examination scores on the performance of students in PSLE, and the second sample for piloting the logit regression model. A randomly selected sample (N= 152) of Std 7 students from cohorts of 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021 were selected from two primary schools in Kgatleng Region. Since the study utilized secondary data sources, the availability of records was a determining factor on the size of the sample. For pilot testing the logit regression model, I purposively selected students from a cohort of 2023 Std 7s students (N = 29) in one primary school due to convenience as well as availability and access to their records.

Data Collection

Secondary data was obtained from records kept by primary schools. Availability of records was a challenge because primary schools relied mostly on hard copies rather than digitized databases. Nonetheless, I developed and used a data extraction instrument to collect secondary data from schools' records in the region. Details extracted from school records included the overall percentage score on mock examination and the corresponding PSLE grade of the same participant. As for the second phase of the study which involved piloting the algorithm derived from data, I collected mock examination scores from the pilot sample. These mock examinations were prepared and standardized at National level by the Ministry of Education & Skills Development.

Ethical Issues

I strived to address ethical issues by obtaining both the ethical clearance from the Ethics Board at Botswana Open University (*Reference no. 9987285071827*) and research permission from the Ministry of Education and Skills Development (*RE: KGATL 1/13/1 V (47)*) respectively. In addition, I consulted prospective primary schools to solicit their consent to allow access into their continuous assessment records. The participation of the primary schools was completely voluntary.

Data Analysis Procedure

Microsoft Excel and statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) for data analysis. The dependent variable (academic success in PSLE grades) was categorical and had dichotomous groups, pass or fail. For the dependent variable, participants who had overall grades A, B or C were classified as a PASS and were coded as 1 whereas participants with overall grades D or E in their PSLE were classified as FAIL and were coded as 0 (see Table 1). The same procedure was used to classify and code data from mock scores of the pilot sample.

Table 1. *Coding of dependent variable*

Dependent Variable Encoding	
Academic success in PSLE	Internal Value
FAIL	0
PASS	1

The predictor variable (mock examination scores) was continuous and measured in percentages. Therefore, I used Binary Logistic Regression to assess the contribution of the predictor variable on the dependent variable (Niu, 2018). The odds ratio was used to evaluate the significance of the coefficient of the predictor variable while Hosmer-Lemeshow test, Chi-Square test statistic, Nagelkerke R Square, Cox & Snell R Square and Classification Percentage Accuracy were used to evaluate the fitted logit regression model. Finally, a predictive logit model was derived.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

To answer research question 1 (*does mock examination scores significantly predict PSLE performance of Std 7 students?*), a Binary logistic regression model was fitted with the predictor variable (mock examination scores). A Chi-Square test statistic output from the logistic regression analysis evaluated whether the fitted logit regression model fits the data any better than the null model without predictors.

Table 2. *Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients*

		Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	73.733	1	.000
	Block	73.733	1	.000
	Model	73.733	1	.000

Examination of Table 2 shows that there was a significant improvement of the fitted logistic regression model compared to the null model ($X^2(1) = 73.733, p < 0.01$). Overall, the logit regression model is showing a very good fit.

The compatibility of the fitted logit regression model was determined by the use of Hosmer-and Lemeshow test. Unlike in Linear regression, p value should be greater than 0.05 for the model to be accepted as a good fit to data.

Table 3. *Hosmer-and Lemeshow Test for Goodness of Fit*

Step	Chi-square	df	Sig.
1	7.912	8	.442

Table 3 shows that $X^2(8) = 7.912$, $p = 0.442 > 0.05$, the model is not significant and thus it indicates that the logit regression model is a good fit to the data and would predict values of PSLE approximately equal to the observed PSLE. This means that the logit regression model is better suited to using mock examination scores as a predictor of the academic success of students.

The variation in the outcome variable was approximated using pseudo R square derived from Cox & Snell R square as well as Nagelkerke R square. These two tests, Cox & Snell R square and Nagelkerke R square, are analogous to the coefficient of determination R^2 in Linear regression (Zewude & Ashine, 2016). According to Mabula (2015), Cox & Snell and Nagelkerke pseudo R square measures the improvement in the logit regression model along a continuum such that any output within the range 0-0.1 represents poor improvement, 0.1-0.3 modest improvement, 0.3-0.5 moderate improvement, and anything beyond 0.5 will denote a strong improvement.

Table 4. Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	92.680 ^a	.384	.578

a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 7 because parameter estimates changed by less than .001.

According to the model summary in Table 4 above, Cox & Snell R^2 indicates that 38.4% change in the dependent variable is explained by the predictor variable, which also reflects a moderate improvement in the fit over the baseline model. On the other hand, Nagelkerke R^2 also indicates that 57.8% of the change in dependent variable can be accounted to the predictor variable. Nagelkerke R^2 also shows a strong improvement over the null model. Overall, the change in students' academic success explained by the logit regression model raises from 38.4% to 57.8%.

Classification Percentage Accuracy was used to evaluate how well a fitted logit regression model was able to predict the correct group membership on the dependent variable. That is, whether a participant is correctly predicted to fall in the pass or fail group

Table 5. Classification Table

Step 1	Observed	Academic success	Predicted		Percentage Correct
			FAIL	PASS	
			FAIL	23	
PASS	5	111	95.7		
Overall Percentage					88.2

a. The cut value is .500

Examination of Table 5 shows that the percentage accuracy of classification (PAC= 88.2%) was very good. Furthermore, the percentage accuracy of classification of the fitted logit regression model was relatively higher in comparison to the null model (PAC = 76.3%). The fitted logit regression model exhibits a good sensitivity since among the cases observed to fall in the pass group, 95.7% were correctly predicted to fall in the same group based on the model.

I further used odds ratio in order to evaluate the significance of coefficients of the predictor variable (Mock exam scores). According to Mabula (2015), odds ratio greater than 1 indicates that the chances of falling into a target group is greater than the chance of falling into the non-target group.

Table 6. Variables in the Equation

		B	S.E.	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	95.0% EXP(B)	
								Lower	Upper
Step 1 ^a	Mock Exam score	.185	.035	28.253	1	.000	1.203	1.124	1.288
	Constant	-8.751	1.811	23.360	1	.000	.000		

a. Variable(s) entered on step 1: MOCK.

As such, upon examination of Table 6, it is clear that the estimated odds ratio of 1.203 indicates that the odds of a Std 7 student who scores 50% and more in his or her mock examinations are 1.203 times more likely to pass PSLE compared to a Std 7 student who performs poorly in his or her mock exams. At 95% Confidence Interval of 1.24 to 1.288, the CI does not cross 1. Similarly, the regression coefficient Beta is significant ($B = 0.185$, $p < 0.01$). This implies that an increase in the predictor variable (mock exam scores) will also lead to an increase in the odds of passing the Primary School Leaving Examinations (PSLE).

Pilot of the Binary Logistic Regression Model

The results of the evaluation of the fitted logit regression model evidenced that the model fits the data very well and that it accurately predicts the academic success (pass or fail) of Std 7 students in Primary School Leaving Examinations (PSLE). Hence I went further on to address and respond to the second research question; *what is the predicted PSLE performance of 2023 cohort of Std 7 students?* In order to answer this question, a sample of Std 7 students ($N = 29$) who were candidates for the 2023 PSLE was used. PSLE is a Botswana based terminal assessment tool used to mark the transition of primary school students into secondary education. Mock examination scores of these students were entered into the logit regression model derived from previous data. The logit regression model is given by;

$$\log \frac{P(x)}{1 - P(x)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1$$

And the fitted logit regression model derived from Table 6 above, which displays the variables in the equation, transformed into;

$$\log \frac{P(x)}{1 - P(x)} = -8.75149 + (0.18476X_1)$$

In order to predict the academic success (pass or fail in PSLE) of the sampled cohort of 2023, I used spreadsheet in MS Excel. I took three (3) steps; 1) used the logit regression model to generate predicted logit scores for each candidate, 2) transformed the predicted logit scores into odds or predicted probabilities, 3) and

then transformed the predicted probabilities into group membership. Step 1 and 2 were computed in spread sheet while for step 3, data was transferred into SPSS.

Step 1: Generated predicted logit scores for each candidate by using the model;

$$\text{predicted}_{\text{logit}} = -8.75149 + (0.18476X_1)$$

Step 2: Predicted logit scores were transformed into predicted probabilities for each candidate by utilizing the following algorithm;

$$\text{predicted}_{\text{probabilities}} = \frac{e^{\text{predicted}_{\text{logit}}}}{1 + e^{\text{predicted}_{\text{logit}}}}$$

Step 3: Involved assigning group membership to each candidate to predict whether they will fall into the target group (pass = 1) or non-target group (fail = 0). First, I transferred the predicted probabilities from spreadsheet in MS Excel to SPSS. In SPSS, I transformed the predicted probabilities or odds into different variables by recoding predicted probabilities within a range of 0.0 to 0.49999 as 0 and values greater than 0.50000 as 1. This procedure assigned each candidate a predicted group membership. Descriptive statistics was used to present the overall results.

Table 7. Predicted academic success using derived logit regression model

		Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
Predicted PSLE 2023	Fail	15	51.7	.48	.509
	Pass	14	48.3		
	Total	29	100.0		

The built logit regression model predicts that out of 29 Std 7 PSLE candidates sampled for the pilot test, 15 (51.7%) students will pass by obtaining grades A, B and/or C while 14 (48.3%) will fail the 2023 Primary School Leaving Examinations by obtaining grades D and/or E. According to the results, most students will be clustered closer to the pass/fail margin (M = 0.48, SD = 0.509).

CONCLUSION

The main objective of the study was to assess the influence of mock examination scores on the performance of standard 7 students in their final examination. Fitted logistic regression model revealed that scores of standardized mock examinations administered prior to primary school terminal examinations across the country were a significant predictor for academic success of Std. 7 students later on in their Primary School Leaving Examinations. Therefore, mock examinations can be considered as a significant determinant of primary school students' performance in Kgatleng region in Botswana.

Implications of the study

Based on the findings of the study, mock examinations are a determinant of academic success in Std 7 transition examinations and as such, primary school teachers can use mock examination scores and the derived logit regression model as a viable alternative method to forecasting PSLE scores of candidates in their classrooms. Predicting PSLE achievement using mock exam scores may serve as a point of departure for

primary school teachers to devise appropriate and corrective strategies to implement well in time so as to adjust and enhance learning as well as to promote academic success.

Suggestions and recommendations

A more robust study can be carried out, with a broadened population, rigorous sampling and determination of prediction accuracy of the model. Prediction accuracy of the model is more likely to help to determine whether the predicted outcome of prospective PSLE candidates matches their actual academic achievement. I also suggest that a similar study with more determinants of academic performance should be carried out since in reality, academic success is influenced by multitudes of factors and thus it is more logical to include as many predictors as possible to explain variance in academic performance of students.

Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The author reports that there are no competing interests to declare. The author also reports that there was no financial or non-financial support in the preparation of this work. This research study complies with research publishing ethics.

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